

Synthesis and characterization of metal complexes of flumequine, oxolinic acid, ofloxacin and ciprofloxacin

B. S. Sekhon* and Juhi Srivastava

Department of Biochemistry and Chemistry, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana-141 004, Punjab, India

E-mail : sekhon224@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 8 June 2007, accepted 20 September 2007

Abstract : The metal complexes of flumequine (FLU), oxolinic acid (OXO), ofloxacin (OFL) and ciprofloxacin (CIP) were synthesized and characterized by elemental analyses and IR spectral studies. Spectral data suggest that (i) Cu^{II} and VO^{II} -1,10-phenanthroline mixed system binds through 4-keto group and the ionized 3-carboxylic acid group of FLU, (ii) 4-keto group and the ionized 3-carboxylic acid group of CIP coordinates with Ce^{III} , Ag^{I} and VO^{II} , (iii) Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} bind through 4-keto group of OXO. The $-\text{NO}_2$ group of silver picrate coordinate to deprotonated $-\text{COOH}$ group of each OFL and CIP.

Keywords : Flumequine, oxolinic acid, ofloxacin, ciprofloxacin, metal complexes of fluoroquinolones.

Quinolones are synthetic antibacterial agents widely used in clinical practice. Oxolinic acid (5-ethyl-5,8-dihydro-8-oxo[1,3]dioxolo[4,5-g]quinoline-7-carboxylic acid, OXO) belongs to this class (structure I) and is authorized in veterinary medicine for use in fin fish, calves, pigs and poultry. Fluoroquinolone antibiotics are one of the most successful classes of drugs. They are considered to be well tolerated drugs with relatively limited adverse effects^{1,2} so that the use of several compounds of the series in therapy is increasing. Fluoroquinolones are a group of potent synthetic antibiotics that are widely used in human and veterinary medicines³. Flumequine (9-fluoro-6,7-dihydro-5-methyl-1-oxo-1*H*,5*H*-benzo[*ij*]-quinolizine-2-carboxylic acid, structure II-FLU), ofloxacin ((+/-)-9-fluoro-2,3-dihydro-3-methyl-10-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-7-oxo-7*H*-pyrido[1,2,3-*de*]-1,4-benzoxazine-6-carboxylic acid, structure III-OFL), ciprofloxacin (1-cyclopropyl-6-fluoro-1,4-dihydro-4-oxo-7-(1-piperazinyl)-3-quinolinecarboxylic acid, structure IV-CIP) are members

of this large family and are used for the treatment of certain diseases caused by various Gram negative and some Gram positive microorganisms⁴. It was found that quinolones react with several metal ions and the crystal structures of boron, cadmium, calcium, cerium, cobalt, copper, iron, magnesium, nickel, silver and zinc complexes have been reported^{5,6}. Some studies on the complexes of fluoroquinolones with metal ions have been reported⁷⁻¹¹.

The availability of fluoroquinolone antibiotics to interact with some cellular components is mediated by their complexation with divalent metal cations. The synthesis and characterization of new metal complexes with quinolone and fluoroquinolone antibacterials are of great importance for understanding the drug-metal ion interaction and for their potential for pharmacological use. Furthermore, complex formation with divalent cations of transition metals would be of far greater interest and possible importance, since it has been reported that many enzymes having nucleic acids as substrates or templates contain a nonmagnesium divalent cation¹². The present aim was to isolate and characterize the new complexes of ligands flumequine, oxolinic acid, ofloxacin and ciprofloxacin with some transition metal ions Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , VO^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} and silver picrate.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization of fluoroquinolones metal complexes : The stoichiometry of the metal complexes as deduced from elemental analysis is given in

Table 1. Analytical and physical characteristics of ligands and their metal complexes

Compd.	T_M (°C)	Elemental analysis (%) :		
		Calcd. (Found)		
Flumequine (FLU)				
FLUM (White)	254	64.35	4.62	5.36
$C_{14}H_{12}FNO_3$		(64.20)	(4.60)	(5.26)
$Cu(C_{14}H_{11}FNO_3)_2$ (Bluish green)	>280	57.57	3.79	4.79
		(54.74)	(3.59)	(4.72)
$Ni(C_{14}H_{11}FNO_3) \cdot H_2O$ (Sea green)	>280	49.89	4.15	3.88
		(46.95)	(4.13)	(4.78)
$Zn(C_{14}H_{11}FNO_3)_2$ (White)	258	57.39	3.78	4.78
		(59.69)	(3.93)	(4.99)
$VO(C_{14}H_{11}FNO_3)_2$ (Green)	240	49.06	3.77	4.76
		(54.75)	(3.70)	(4.81)
$Co(C_{14}H_{11}FNO_3)_2$ (Bluish white)	250	60.06	3.96	5.00
		(61.64)	(3.85)	(5.16)
$(C_6H_2N_3O_7Ag)_2(C_{14}H_{11}FNO_3)$ (Dark yellow)	>290	40.36	2.86	10.86
		(33.63)	(1.04)	(7.79)
$VOSO_4(C_{14}H_{11}FNO_3)$ (Dull green)	>280	48.83	3.78	6.57
		(47.74)	(3.46)	(5.81)
Oxolinic acid (OXO)				
OXO (White)	>300	59.77	4.24	5.36
$C_{13}H_{11}NO_5$		(59.67)	(4.31)	(5.38)
$Cu(C_{13}H_{10}NO_5)OH$ (Blue)	>280	45.82	3.25	4.11
		(46.41)	(2.73)	(4.31)
$Ni(C_{13}H_{10}NO_5)_2$ (Light blue)	>280	48.94	3.15	4.39
		(48.73)	(2.72)	(4.98)
Ciprofloxacin (CIP)				
CIP (White)	258	55.50	5.20	11.47
$C_{17}H_{18}FN_3O_3 \cdot HCl$		(55.45)	(5.15)	(11.42)
$Ce(C_{17}H_{17}FN_3O_3(OH^-)_2) \cdot H_2O$ (White)	>260	36.95	3.83	7.60
		(37.73)	(3.64)	(7.60)
$VOSO_4(C_{17}H_{17}FN_3O_3)$ (Dull green)	>280	41.38	3.47	8.51
		(41.66)	(3.92)	(8.46)
$AgNO_3(C_{17}H_{17}FN_3O_3) \cdot 3H_2O$ (Brown)	>250	36.77	3.63	10.09
		(36.11)	(2.24)	(9.84)
$C_6H_2N_3O_7Ag(C_{17}H_{17}FN_3O_3)$ $HCl \cdot 2H_2O$ (Yellow)	>250	37.43	3.14	11.38
		(37.34)	(1.92)	(11.06)
Ofloxacin (OFL)				
$C_{18}H_{20}FN_3O_4$	253	59.82	5.57	11.62
		(59.82)	(5.37)	(11.52)
$VO(C_{18}H_{19}FN_3O_4)(OH^-)_2 \cdot H_2O$ (Green)	240	45.09	4.82	8.74
		(45.11)	(4.52)	(8.72)
$C_6H_2N_3O_7Ag(C_{18}H_{19}FN_3O_4)_2$ (Bottle green)	280	47.64	3.61	11.90
		(46.42)	(3.32)	(10.89)

Table 1. The results indicate that Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and VO^{II} formed complexes of stoichiometry 1 : 2 (M : L); Ni^{II} 1 : 1; Co^{II} 1 : 3; silver picrate (AgP) 2 : 1 with flumequine (FLU). In case of oxolinic acid (OXO), Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} formed 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (M : L) complexes respectively. The stoichiometry of the ciprofloxacin complexes was found to be 1 : 1 for Ce^{III} , VO^{II} , Ag^I and AgP. VO^{II} and AgP formed 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with ofloxacin (OFL) respectively. In case of mixed ligand complex of $VOSO_4$ with FLU and 1,10-phenathroline, the stoichiometry was found to be 1 : 1 : 1.

IR spectra :

The representative IR absorption bands of ligands (FLU, OXO, CIP and OFL) and their metal complexes are summarized in Table 2. Comparing the main IR frequencies of metal complexes with that of ligands, the following observations were made :

Metal-ciprofloxacin (CIP) complexes : The IR spectra of quinolones are most indicative in the region 1800–1300 cm^{-1} . The characteristic band for the $\nu_{C=O}$ vibration of the carboxylic group in ciprofloxacin hydrochloride hydrate is at 1707 cm^{-1} ¹³. In the IR spectra of ciprofloxacin and ciprofloxacin hexahydrate, there are no analogous peaks due to the deprotonation of COOH group¹⁴. Some authors have pointed out that ionic carboxylates show no carbonyl band around 1700 cm^{-1} , but instead have two absorption bands due to the asymmetric ($\nu_{asy}(O-C-O)$) and symmetric ($\nu_{sy}(O-C-O)$) stretching vibrations that occur in the ranges 1610–1550 and 1400–1280 cm^{-1} , respectively¹⁵. The anionic ofloxacin ligand coordination through the 4-keto and 3-carboxylate oxygens forming 1 : 2 Mg : OFL complexes has been reported¹⁶.

The $\nu_{C=O}$ due to 3-carboxylic group at 1707.7 cm^{-1} and $\nu_{C=O}$ due to 4-keto group at 1623.8 cm^{-1} for CIP disappeared in the IR absorption spectra of Ce^{III} complex, but shifted to 1718.4 and 1631.5 cm^{-1} in the IR absorption spectra of VO^{II} complex (Table 1). The disappearance of band at 1707.7 cm^{-1} due to the 3-carboxylic group of CIP in the spectrum of the Ce^{III} -CIP complex indicates that 3-carboxylate group participates in the bonding to the metal ion¹⁷. Further, the appearance of two new peaks at 1625.8 and 1417.2 cm^{-1} corresponding to carboxylate antisymmetric and symmetric vibrations respectively in the IR absorption spectra of Ce^{III} complex confirms participation of 3-carboxylate group of CIP. The disappearance of band at 1623.8 cm^{-1} due to 4-keto group suggests its participation in the bonding to metal. Metal quinolone complexes have been characterized with IR spectra^{18–20}.

It is established that the carboxylate group can act as

Table 2. The characteristics IR absorption bands (cm^{-1}) of ligands and their metal complexes

Compd.	Carboxylic	Ketone	$\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{COO}^-) \nu_{\text{O-H}}$	
	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{COO}^-)$	
Flumequine (FLU)				
FLU ($\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{NO}_3$)	1722.0	1620.5		3439.3
$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{FNO}_3)_2$		1611.2		3390.2
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{FNO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	1720.6	1621.2	1568.1, 1456.0	3528.9
$\text{Zn}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{FNO}_3)_2$	1707.2	–	1596.9, 1441.2	3636.2
$\text{VO}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{FNO}_3)_2$	1725.4	1620.0	1568.8, 1472.2	3436.1
$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{FNO}_3)_3$	1725.2	1620.2	1472.4	3401.5
$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_2\text{N}_3\text{O}_7\text{Ag})(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{FNO}_3)$	1725.5	1622.8	1468.5	3400.9
$\text{VOSO}_4(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{FNO}_3)$ $(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1730.8	1626.0	–	3366.6
Oxolinic acid (OXO)				
OXO ($\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_3$)	1629.4	1468.2		3401.8
$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{NO}_3)\text{OH}$	1616.7	1429.9		3398.1
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{NO}_3)_2$	1646.4	1470.3		3454.9
Ciprofloxacin (CIP)				
CIP ($\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{FN}_3\text{O}_3$)	1707.7	1623.8		3528.8
$\text{Ce}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{FN}_3\text{O}_3)(\text{OH}^-)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	–	1625.8	1471.2	3400.7
$\text{VOSO}_4(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{FN}_3\text{O}_3)$	1718.4	1631.5		3338.6
$\text{AgNO}_3(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{FN}_3\text{O}_3) \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1728	1628.7		3422.1
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_2\text{N}_3\text{O}_7\text{Ag}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{FN}_3\text{O}_3)$ $2\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{HCl}$	1701.6	1631.6, 1611.5		3447.8
Ofloxacin (OFL)				
$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{FN}_3\text{O}_4$	1714.3	1621.7		3422.0
$\text{VO}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{19}\text{FN}_3\text{O}_4)(\text{OH}^-)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	1715.8	1621.8		3409.1
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_2\text{N}_3\text{O}_7\text{Ag}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{19}\text{FN}_3\text{O}_4)$	–	1620.6		3390.2

unidentate, bidentate or as bridging ligand and distinction between these binding states can be made from the frequency separation ($\Delta\nu = [\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{COO}) - \nu_{\text{sy}}(\text{COO})]$) between the symmetric and the asymmetric stretching of this group^{21,22}. By examining the symmetric and the asymmetric stretching vibrations of large number of carboxylate complexes with known crystal structure, Deacon and Phillips²² established the criteria that can be used to distinguish between the three binding states of the carboxylate complexes. These criteria are : (i) unidentate carboxylate complexes exhibit $\Delta\nu$ values which are much larger than those of the ionic salts ($\Delta\nu > 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), (ii)

bidentate or chelating carboxylate complexes, exhibit $\Delta\nu$ significantly smaller than ionic values ($\Delta\nu < 100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), and finally, (iii) bridging complexes show $\Delta\nu$ comparable to the ionic values ($\Delta\nu \approx 150 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The value of $\Delta\nu$ 154.3 cm^{-1} for Ce^{III} complex suggests bridging behavior of 3-carboxylate group of CIP in complex formation.

There was a significant decrease in the intensity of $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ band at 1707.7 cm^{-1} and three new absorption bands appeared at 1585.8 , 1516.7 and 1474.7 cm^{-1} in VO^{II} -CIP complex spectra, thereby, indicating the participation of 4-keto group and the ionized 3-carboxylic acid group of VO^{II} -CIP complex. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ due to 3-carboxylic group at 1707.7 cm^{-1} and $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ due to 4-keto group at 1623.8 cm^{-1} for CIP shifted to 1701.6 and 1631.6 cm^{-1} in the IR absorption spectra of AgP complex while to 1728.0 and 1628.7 cm^{-1} in the IR spectra of Ag^{I} -CIP complex respectively. Further, additional peaks were observed at 1611.5 , 1568.5 and 1474.2 cm^{-1} in AgP-CIP complex and at 1547.5 , 1510.4 and 1466.6 cm^{-1} in Ag^{I} -CIP complex. These observations indicate the participation of 4-keto group and the ionized 3-carboxylic acid group of CIP with Ag^{I} as well as AgP. In addition, the IR absorption bands at 1623.3 cm^{-1} and 1327.7 cm^{-1} due to ν_{NO_2} (asy) and ν_{NO_2} (sy) respectively of AgP disappeared in the spectra of the AgP-CIP complex. These results suggest the participation of $-\text{NO}_2$ groups of AgP with deprotonated 3-COOH group of CIP.

Metal-oxolinic acid complexes : The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ due to 4-keto group at 1629.4 cm^{-1} for OXO shifted to 1616.7 and 1646.4 cm^{-1} in the IR absorption spectra of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes respectively. These observations indicate the coordination of 4-keto group of OXO in the bonding to metal ion. Synthesis and characterization of the neutral mononuclear copper complexes with OXO have been reported and it acts as a deprotonated bidentate ligand and is coordinated to the metal ion through the pyridone and one carboxylate oxygen atoms⁹.

Metal-ofloxacin (OFL) complexes : The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ due to 3-carboxylic acid group of OFL disappeared in the spectra of the AgP-OFL complex indicating, thereby, the participation of 3-COO⁻ group of OFL in complexation with AgP. The IR absorption bands of AgP due to ν_{NO_2} (asy) at 1623.3 cm^{-1} shifted to 1620.6 cm^{-1} while ν_{NO_2} (sym) at 1327.7 cm^{-1} disappeared in the spectra of the AgP-OFL complex. These results suggest the participation of $-\text{NO}_2$ group of AgP with deprotonated 3-COOH group of OFL. Several coordination compound formed between Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with ofloxacin have been synthesized and characterised^{18,23}.

Metal-flumequine (FLU) complexes : In the IR absorption spectra of FLU, the $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ band due to 3-carboxylic group at 1722.0 cm^{-1} shifted to 1720.6 for Ni^{II} , 1707.2 for Zn^{II} , 1725.4 for VO^{II} , 1725.2 for Co^{II} , 1725.5 for AgP and 1730.8 cm^{-1} for VO^{II} -1,10-phenanthroline system. However, the $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ (carboxylic) peak for FLU disappeared in the spectra of Cu^{II} complex. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ band observed at 1620.5 cm^{-1} due to 4-keto group in FLU was found at 1611.2 for Cu^{II} , 1621.2 for Ni^{II} , 1620.0 for VO^{II} , 1596.9 for Zn^{II} , 1620.2 for Co^{II} , 1622.8 for AgP and 1626.0 cm^{-1} for VO^{II} -1,10-phenanthroline system. For VO^{II} -1,10-phenanthroline mixed complex, new peaks at 1588.5 , 1528.3 and 1481.6 cm^{-1} were observed in spectrum of the complex. These results also suggest participation of 3-COO⁻ and 4-keto oxygen atoms with metal ions.

Experimental

Flumequine, $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{NFO}_3$, F.W. 261.26; oxolinic acid, $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_5$, F.W. 261.2; ofloxacin, $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{FN}_3\text{O}_4$, F.W. 361.368 and ciprofloxacin hydrochloride, $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{FN}_3\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{HCl}$, F.W. 367.84 were procured from M.P. Biochemicals, Inc.

Preparation of metal-flumequine complexes : Two mmol (522.52 mg) of flumequine was dissolved in 10 ml of ethanol and 1 mmol of each metal salt [copper nitrate, nickel nitrate, zinc sulphate, vanadyl sulphate, cobalt chloride and silver picrate] was dissolved in 10 ml of water. The ligand solution was added slowly drop by drop to each metal ion solution and the pH was adjusted to about 8. The resulting solutions were reduced to half of its volume on water-bath and the products obtained after cooling were filtered and dried at 60°C and kept in vacuum desiccators over calcium chloride. The flumequine- VO^{II} -1,10-phenanthroline mixed ligand complex was prepared by mixing drop by drop one mmol each of flumequine and 1,10-phenanthroline in 5 ml of ethanol to one mmol of $\text{VO}^{\text{II}}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 5 ml of water. The resulting solution was reduced to half of its volume on water-bath and product obtained was filtered and dried at 60°C and kept in vacuum desiccators over calcium chloride.

Preparation of metal-oxolinic acid complexes : Two mmol (522.4 mg) of oxolinic acid was dissolved in 50 ml of DMF and 1 mmol of each solid metal salt [copper nitrate, nickel nitrate] was added drop by drop to this ligand solution. The pH of the resulting solution was adjusted to about 8 and the solutions were reduced to half of its volume and the products obtained with different metals were filtered and dried at 60°C and kept in vacuum desiccators over calcium chloride.

Preparation of metal-ciprofloxacin complexes : Two mmol (735.68 mg) of ciprofloxacin was dissolved in 10 ml of water and one mmol of each metal salt [AgNO_3 , silver picrate, Ce^{III} sulphate] was dissolved in 10 ml of water. The ligand solution was added drop by drop to metal salt solution. The pH of resulting solution was adjusted to about 5.5 for silver picrate complex and to about pH 3.5 for AgNO_3 complex. The resulting solution was reduced to half of its volume on water-bath and the product obtained was filtered and dried at 60°C and kept in vacuum desiccators over calcium chloride. For mixed ligand complex, one mmol each of $\text{VO}^{\text{II}}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, silver picrate and ciprofloxacin were mixed in water. The resulting solutions were reduced to half of its volume on water-bath and the product obtained were filtered and dried at 60°C and kept in vacuum desiccators over calcium chloride.

Preparation of metal-ofloxacin complexes : One mmol (361.4 mg) of ofloxacin was dissolved in 10 ml of acetonitrile. 0.5 mmol $\text{VO}^{\text{II}}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and one mmol of silver picrate were separately dissolved in 10 ml of water. The ligand solution was added slowly drop by drop to metal ion solution and the resulting solutions was reduced to half of its volume on water-bath and the product obtained were filtered and dried at 60°C and kept in vacuum desiccators over calcium chloride.

Methods of analysis : Melting points were determined on Thiele's apparatus using open capillary tube. Elemental analysis (C, H and N) of the ligands and the synthesized complexes were carried out at Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, Punjab University, Chandigarh. The IR spectra of the ligands and their solid metal complexes were recorded in KBr pellets in the region $4000\text{--}500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, Punjab University, Chandigarh and National Institute of Pharmaceutical Education and Research, Mohali, Punjab.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to the UGC, New Delhi for financial support and the Head, Department of Biochemistry & Chemistry, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana for facilities.

References

1. R. Stahlmann and H. Lode, *Drugs*, 1999, **58** (Suppl. 2), 37.
2. B. A. Lipsky and C. A. Baker, *Clin. Infect. Dis.*, 1999, **28**, 352.
3. C. Walsh, "Antibiotics : Actions, Origins, Resistance", ASM Press, Washington, DC, 2003.
4. J. E. F. Reynolds, in "The Extra Pharmacopeia", 30th ed., The

- Pharmaceutical Press, London, 1993, pp. 145-147.
- I. Turel, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2002, **232**, 27 and references therein.
 - I. Turel, A. Golobic, A. Klavzar, B. Pilhar, P. Buglyo, E. Tolis, D. Rehder and K. Specic, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2003, **95**, 199.
 - Z. H. Chohan, C. T. Supuran and A. Scozzafava, *J. Enz. Inhibit. Med. Chem.*, 2005, **20**, 303.
 - J. R. Anaconda and C. Toledo, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2001, **26**, 228.
 - G. Psomas, A. Tarushi, E. K. Efthimiadou, Y. Sanakis, C. P. Raptopoulou and N. Katsaros, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2006, **100**, 1764.
 - N. Jimenez-Garrido, L. Perello, R. Ortiz, G. Alzuet, M. Gonzalez-Alvarez, E. Canton, M. Liu-Gonzalez, S. Garcia-Granda and M. Perez-Priede, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2005, **99**, 677.
 - M. Cygler and C. P. Huber, *Acta Cryst.*, 1985, **C41**, 1052.
 - H. Park, C. Oh, H. Lee, J. G. Choi, B. Jung and K. Bark, *Bull. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **27**, 2002.
 - I. Turel, I. Leban and N. Bukovec, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1997, **66**, 241.
 - I. Turel, P. Bukovec and M. Quirós, *Int. J. Pharm.*, 1997, **152**, 59.
 - F. Gao, P. Yang, J. Xie and H. Wang, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1995, **60**, 61.
 - P. Drevenšek, J. Košmrlj, G. Giester, T. Skauge, E. Sletten, K. Sepčić and I. Turel, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2006, **100**, 1755.
 - L. J. Bellamy, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", 3rd ed., Chapman and Hall, London, UK, 1975.
 - B. Macias, M. V. Villa, I. Rubio, A. Castineiras and J. Borrás, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2001, **84**, 163.
 - G. P. Wang and Q. F. Lei, *J. Zhejiang University (Science Edition)*, 2003, **30**, 92.
 - A. M. Zupancic, I. Arcon, P. Bukovec and A. Kodre, *Croat. Chem. Acta*, 2002, **75**, 1.
 - K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 4th ed., Wiley, New York, 1986, pp. 230-233.
 - G. B. Deacon and R. J. Phillips, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1980, **33**, 227.
 - V. Uivarosi, S. Neagoe, V. Aldea and A. Nitulescu, *Roum. Arch. Microbiol. Immunol.*, 2001, **60**, 267.